

Recruitment and Selection Process of Huanghai Property Management Company in Qingdao, Shandong, China: Basis for Program Development

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Abstract

The study aimed to assess the extent of implementation of the recruitment and selection process at HuangHai Property Management Company in Qingdao, Shandong, China. The study used a descriptive-survey research design, and the investigation's foremost objective was to ascertain how the recruiting and selection process was being implemented at the company. The variables that were included were anticipation, job analysis, pool development for recruitment, and assessment procedure, deal closing, and onboarding for selection. The study employed the purposive sampling technique selecting managers and staff as respondents. A total of 102 respondents met the criteria of the study concerning the recruitment and selection process. The study found that the company effectively implemented its recruitment process, creating a candidate pool for job offers using both internal and external methods. However, gaps were identified, suggesting the anticipation of the need for more staff observations and managers' perceptions of job analysis. To better understand the job's complexity, context, responsibilities, and practices, the company should conduct proactive analysis of future demands, continuously evaluate potential candidate pools, and generate periodic forecasts of needs. Moreover, the investigation revealed that the company's selection process was effectively implemented, with a successful assessment procedure indicating a candidate's fit for the role and company culture. The onboarding process was methodical and orderly, aiming to encourage commitment and job satisfaction. However, there are still gaps in the data gathered, and the company should focus more on deal closing, particularly signing employment agreements with highly qualified candidates. This suggested that, in order to conduct a specific intervention based on differences in observation applicable to each category of variables, a significant difference in the respondents' observations regarding the extent of the implementation of the recruitment and selection process should be employed. The outcomes of the study served as a foundation to formulate a proposed program development to improve the effectiveness of recruitment and selection process that could be utilized by the involved company.

Keywords: hiring process, program development, recruitment, recruitment and selection process, selection

Introduction

An organization must thrive and survive in the global economy in this age of globalization through effective and efficient methods. Every employer must encourage and effectively employ recruitment and selection process in the workplace. It is directly related to organizational effectiveness and is dependent on the company having qualified workers (Karim et al., 2021).

According to Chhotala and Thaker (2022), effective management should identify human resource needs in the company. The company's results are enhanced as an outcome of improved recruitment and selection process. If a company has competent human resources, they will be able to provide products of the highest quality for society, and this is only feasible with meticulous and effective candidate selection. Every company should adhere to effective recruitment for the right selection.

As societies developed and employment opportunities expanded, there was a growing need to understand how to assess applicants' knowledge, skills, abilities, and other factors, how to determine which assessment methods are most appropriate for applicants, how to attract the most qualified applicants to apply, and how to select those with both the highest potential to perform and a good fit with the recruiting organization (Potonik et al., 2021). These are only a few of the broad issues that recruitment and selection scholars have raised and debated over the years.

Clearly, it is fundamental in the present research, which is based on person-organizational fit theory, to identify gaps in the recruiting and selection process, take efforts to eliminate or reduce them, and make improvement strategies by developing a program.

As a result, there are several implications for the recruitment and selection of candidates. For instance, the job specification may need to be revised to reflect which tasks are still necessary, which should be added, and which can be automated or replaced by technology. The selection and recruitment processes have also been significantly impacted by shifting labor regulations, an expanding economy, and the rise of precarious work. For example, selection through applications managed by digital platforms that establish the minimum cut-off criteria to select and manage the people who perform the work (Duggan et al., 2019).

Furthermore, according to a study conducted in China by Ye (2022), the process of recruiting and selection is so intricate that issues may arise if hiring managers overlook important elements. Because the process is dynamic, several plans for recruiting and selection

must be developed for varying needs, roles, and organizations. As a result, it is crucial to recognize challenges with hiring and choosing employees and take action to reduce or eliminate them.

In line with this, the purpose of this research was to determine the extent to which HuangHai Property Management Company in Qingdao, Shandong, China, implemented recruitment and selection process. The information gathered from the research were utilized in developing a proposed program to improve the effectiveness of recruitment and selection process that the involved company may employ.

Methods

The study is anchored in the Person-Organization Fit Theory by Amy L. Kristof in 1996. According to this theory, a person's essential values, beliefs, ethics, and purpose should be in line with those of the company they work for. The impact of recruiting and selection on person and organizational performance are increasingly being acknowledged. It is a way of choosing qualified candidates who have the right mindset and viewpoints to fit in with the workplace culture.

The study involved managers and staff as respondents. These respondents are from HuangHai Property Management Company in Qingdao, Shandong, China, which is the research locale of the study. These respondents are regular employees who have worked for the company for at least a year; they are at least bachelor's degree holders; and they are familiar with the recruitment and selection process of the chosen company.

The study used a descriptive-survey research design, and the investigation's foremost objective was to ascertain how the recruiting and selection process was being implemented at HuangHai Property Management Company in Qingdao, Shandong, China.

Additionally, the study employed the purposive sampling technique, in which groups of individuals were chosen because they possessed qualities that the study needed or demanded. To best address the study's problems, this was employed to gain access to a specific fraction of the population that shares specified features (Nikolopoulou, 2023b).

The criteria that were used to select respondents were the following: (1) the respondents who are regular employees; (2) the respondents who have knowledge and involvement in the recruitment and selection process of the company; and (3) the respondents with at least a bachelor's degree.

Table 1

Respondents of the Study

HuangHai Company	Property Management	Population Size	Sample Size
1. Managers		50	11
2. Staff		450	91
Total		500	102

The instrument of the study was constructed based on related literature, theory, and supporting studies. The instrument that was utilized in conducting the investigation was a self-made survey questionnaire.

The instrument of the study was composed of two parts. Part 1 of the research instrument centered on the profiles of respondents, both managers and staff. They were asked about their age, sex, educational attainment, designation, and years of employment at the company.

Part 2 of the research instrument focused on the extent to which the recruitment and selection process is being implemented. This was centered on variables that involve recruitment and selection. For recruitment, it elicited items about anticipation, job analysis, and pool development, while for selection, it elicited items about assessment procedures, deal closing, and onboarding.

Both respondents, manager, and staff, were asked to describe the extent of implementation of the recruitment and selection process at HuangHai Property Management Company in Qingdao, Shandong, China, with their honest agreement and disagreement on the above items.

The instrument of the study was subject to pilot testing before the actual gathering of data. This involved respondents who were not involved in the actual investigation of the study. This also included managers and staff from Qingdao, Shandong, China. The results of the pilot study were subjected to Cronbach's alpha for reliability testing. When the results were acceptable, the researcher asked for the approval of the adviser to begin the actual conduct of the study.

Before the study was conducted, the researcher identified the population size of employees from HuangHai Property Management Company in Qingdao, Shandong, China and then the sample size was drawn based on the criteria set. This sample size included both managers and staff members. The senior management of the selected company was then contacted to request authorization to conduct the actual study. When the management approved the communication letter of request (Appendix A) that the researcher submitted, the research procedure started.

The following ethical considerations were upheld throughout conducting the study: Informed Consent and Voluntary Participation, Anonymity and Confidentiality, and Self-Determination (Autonomy).

The following statistical tools were used to analyze and interpret the gathered data from the study's investigation: Frequency and Percentage Distribution, Weighted Mean, Analysis of Variance, and t-test

Results

Table 2

The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-29 years old	29	28.43
30-39 years old	39	38.24
40-49 years old	20	19.61
50-59 years old	11	10.78
60 years old and older	3	2.94
Total	102	100.00

Based on the gathered data, it shows that 29 (28.43%) of the respondents involved in the survey belonged to the age bracket of 20–29 years old, 39 (38.24%) were in the 30–39 years old age bracket, 20 (19.61%) were in the 40–49 years old age bracket, 11 (10.78%) were in the 50–59 years old age bracket, and only 3 (2.94%) were in the 60 years old and older age bracket.

Table 3

The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	53	51.96
Female	49	48.04
Total	102	100.00

Based on the gathered data, it shows that 53 (51.96%) of the respondents involved in the survey are males, while 49 (48.04%) are females.

Table 4

The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor's Degree	67	65.69
Master's Degree	24	23.53
Doctoral Degree	11	10.78
Total	102	100.00

Based on the gathered data, it shows that 67 (65.69%) of the respondents involved in the survey have at least bachelor's degrees, 24 (23.53%) of which have master's degrees, and 11 (10.78%) of them have doctoral degrees.

Table 5

The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Designation

Designation	Frequency	Percentage
Manager	11	10.78
Staff	91	89.22
Total	102	100.00

Based on the gathered data, it shows that 11 (10.78%) of the respondents involved in the survey were managers, while 91 (89.22%) were staff.

Table 6

The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Years of Employment at the Company

Years of Employment at the Company	Frequency	Percentage
1-5 years of employment	35	34.31
6-10 years of employment	31	30.39
11-15 years of employment	22	21.57
16-20 years of employment	9	8.82
21 years and above of employment	5	4.90
Total	102	100.00

Based on the gathered data, it shows that 35 (34.31%) of the respondents involved in the survey have been employed for 1–5 years at the company, 31 (30.39%) have been employed for 6–10 years, 22 (21.57%) have been employed for 11–15 years, 9 (8.82%) have been employed for 16–20 years, and 5 (4.90%) have been employed for 21 years and above at the company.

Table 7

The Weighted Mean of the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment Process in Terms of Needs Anticipation

Needs Anticipation	Managers		Staff	
	WM	QI	WM	QI
1. The company conducts a proactive analysis of future needs and continually assesses the situation of some of the top talent that is bound to leave.	3.64	LgE	3.81	LgE
2. The company conducts a review of the proposed job content and organizational structure to ensure that the job advertisement is designed in a way that fully meets the needs of the organization.	3.36	SE	3.96	LgE
3. The company conducts an intake meeting with the hiring manager and/or person-in-charge who are involved in making hiring decisions to fully understand the unique hiring needs.	3.55	LgE	3.71	LgE
4. The company develops a recruitment plan to help	3.00	SE	3.55	LgE

streamline hiring processes and know what roles need to be filled in the near future.				
5. The company aligns its goals and skills gap with hiring needs in order to strategically plan for the year ahead.	3.64	LgE	3.58	LgE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.44	LgE	3.72	LgE

Note. Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Very Large Extent-VLgE); 3.41-4.20 (Large Extent-LgE); 2.61-3.40 (Some Extent-SE); 1.81-2.60 (Little Extent-LtE); 1.00-1.80 (Very Little Extent-VLtE)

Based on assessments of the managers, items nos. 1 and 5, with both weighted mean scores of 3.64 and both interpreted as “large extent,” obtained the highest extent of implementation of the recruitment process in terms of needs anticipation, while item no. 4 received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean score of 3.00 and interpreted as “some extent.”

Table 8

The Weighted Mean of the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment Process in Terms of Job Analysis

Job Analysis	Managers		Staff	
	WM	QI	WM	QI
1. The company ensures that adequate and relevant information about the organization and job is provided to the candidate at the time of recruitment.	3.18	SE	4.23	VLgE
2. The company ensures the right fit between the job and the potential employee and determines how employee performance will be assessed.	3.18	SE	4.30	VLgE
3. The company effectively identifies the tasks and duties required for the role by having a meeting with someone familiar with the position, such as the incumbent and their direct managers.	3.27	SE	4.14	LgE
4. The company effectively lists the duties that are expected of the employee as well as an in-depth understanding of the business objectives for the role.	3.55	LgE	3.82	LgE
5. The company lists the skills and attributes needed by the potential candidates and even discovers new ways to fine-tune the role for greater efficacy.	3.00	SE	4.07	LgE
6. The company conducts consistency in the hiring process, whereby all individuals applying to the same position go through the same process and are measured against the same criteria and standards.	3.36	SE	3.93	LgE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.26	SE	4.08	LgE

Note. Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Very Large Extent-VLgE); 3.41-4.20 (Large Extent-LgE); 2.61-3.40 (Some Extent-SE); 1.81-2.60 (Little Extent-LtE); 1.00-1.80 (Very Little Extent-VLtE)

Based on assessments of the managers, item no. 4, with a weighted mean score of 3.55 and interpreted as “large extent,” obtained the highest extent of implementation of the recruitment process in terms of job analysis, while item no. 5 received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean score of 3.00 and interpreted as “some extent.”

Table 9

The Weighted Mean of the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment Process in Terms of Pool Development

Pool Development	Managers		Staff	
	WM	QI	WM	QI
1. The company develops an internal sourcing process for candidates that is based on a formal means of planning for anticipated vacancies, retirements, mergers, and acquisitions.	4.00	LgE	4.15	LgE
2. The company develops expansion plans in line with employee promotion and succession planning.	4.00	LgE	4.22	VLgE
3. The company enforces the review of the succession plan whenever a vacancy is available or a need to fill a position surfaces.	4.09	LgE	4.09	LgE
4. The company ensures that it widens the pool of candidates available for a position to ensure that it attracts suitable candidates for the job.	3.91	LgE	3.86	LgE
5. The company makes use of e-recruiting systems that are cost-effective, which can allow an organization to quickly collect, store, and receive information, and uses this information for the purpose of external sourcing in this new normal of the recruitment process.	3.55	LgE	4.10	LgE
6. The company develops a good system of referrals that is immensely effective and economical in developing external sourcing.	3.73	LgE	4.00	LgE
7. The company looks at the sort of background and experience that the candidates are expected to have to fit into the business model and company culture.	3.82	LgE	3.93	LgE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.87	LgE	4.05	LgE

Note. Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Very Large Extent-VLgE); 3.41-4.20 (Large Extent-LgE); 2.61-3.40 (Some Extent-SE); 1.81-2.60 (Little Extent-LtE); 1.00-1.80 (Very Little Extent-VLtE)

Based on assessments of the managers, item no. 3, with a weighted mean score of 4.09 and interpreted as “large extent,” obtained the highest extent of implementation of the recruitment process in terms of pool development, while item no. 5 received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean score of 3.55 and interpreted as “large extent.”

Table 10

The Summary of the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment Process

Recruitment Process	Managers		Staff	
	WM	QI	WM	QI
1. Needs Anticipation	3.44	LgE	3.72	LgE
2. Job Analysis	3.26	SE	4.08	LgE
3. Pool Development	3.87	LgE	4.05	LgE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.52	LgE	3.95	LgE

Note. Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Very Large Extent-VLgE); 3.41-4.20 (Large Extent-LgE); 2.61-3.40 (Some Extent-SE); 1.81-2.60 (Little Extent-LtE); 1.00-1.80 (Very Little Extent-VLtE)

Based on assessments of the managers, item no. 3, with a weighted mean score of 3.87 and interpreted as “large extent,” obtained the highest extent of implementation of the recruitment process in terms of its variables, while item no. 2 received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean score of 3.26 and interpreted as “some extent.”

Table 11

The Weighted Mean of the Extent of Implementation of the Selection Process in Terms of Assessment Procedure

Assessment Procedure	Managers		Staff	
	WM	QI	WM	QI
1. The company effectively selects candidates strictly based on merit, education, qualities, expertise, and experience.	3.82	LgE	4.01	LgE
2. The company develops well-trained, motivated, and high-caliber interviewers to assess candidates for suitability for the position.	4.00	LgE	4.05	LgE
3. The company implements an effective interviewing procedure that employs rigorous interviews, detailed reference checking, and the inclusion of top stakeholders for the position.	4.09	LgE	3.85	LgE
4. The company effectively implements assessment methods that include work samples, job simulations, cognitive ability testing, and job trials.	3.82	LgE	3.67	LgE
5. The company identifies and implements assessment methods to select employees that are most effective in this new normal of the hiring process.	3.91	LgE	3.76	LgE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.93	LgE	3.87	LgE

Note. Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Very Large Extent-VLgE); 3.41-4.20 (Large Extent-LgE); 2.61-3.40 (Some Extent-SE); 1.81-2.60 (Little Extent-LtE); 1.00-1.80 (Very Little Extent-VLtE)

Based on assessments of the managers, item no. 3, with a weighted mean score of 4.09 and interpreted as “large extent,” obtained the highest extent of implementation of the selection process in terms of assessment procedure, while item no. 4 received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean score of 3.82 and interpreted as “large extent.”

Table 12

The Weighted Mean of the Extent of Implementation of the Selection Process in Terms of Deal Closing

Deal Closing	Managers		Staff	
	WM	QI	WM	QI
1. The company employs an efficient and effective manner to close the deal with mutual benefits for both candidates and the organization.	3.09	SE	3.76	LgE
2. The company ensures that transparency is presented to build trust between candidates and the organization, so there are no last-minute surprises.	2.82	SE	3.87	LgE
3. The company puts candidates on display, pointing out their shortcomings to identify their strengths, weaknesses, and "fit" for a role.	3.18	SE	3.67	LgE
4. The company ensures honesty by offering them the truth about the role, organization, compensation, and benefits.	3.36	SE	3.49	LgE
5. The company checks in often with candidates, confirms whether they still feel comfortable and excited about the opportunity, and goes over any concerns.	3.00	SE	3.63	LgE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.09	SE	3.68	LgE

Note. Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Very Large Extent-VLgE); 3.41-4.20 (Large Extent-LgE); 2.61-3.40 (Some Extent-SE); 1.81-2.60 (Little Extent-LtE); 1.00-1.80 (Very Little Extent-VLtE)

Based on assessments of the managers, item no. 4, with a weighted mean score of 3.36 and interpreted as "some extent," obtained the highest extent of implementation of the selection process in terms of deal closing, while item no. 2 received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean score of 2.82 and interpreted as "some extent."

Table 13

The Weighted Mean of the Extent of Implementation of the Selection Process in Terms of Onboarding

Onboarding	Managers		Staff	
	WM	QI	WM	QI
1. The company develops a systematic integration of the new employees that leads to lower turnover and greater commitment and job satisfaction.	3.73	LgE	3.87	LgE
2. The company effectively orients new recruits on various fronts, such as their own department and other facets of the organization.	4.00	LgE	3.92	LgE
3. The company implements detailed orientation programs with specific milestones and regular progress reports as part of their integration programs.	3.45	LgE	3.78	LgE
4. The company effectively assigns top performers as mentors for new recruits so that their development and satisfaction levels can be elevated.	3.55	LgE	3.56	LgE
5. The company leverages new hire feedback and analytics to inform the human resources	3.55	LgE	3.66	LgE

department about its recruitment plan and optimize it accordingly.

Overall Weighted Mean 3.65 LgE 3.76 LgE

Note. Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Very Large Extent-VLgE); 3.41-4.20 (Large Extent-LgE); 2.61-3.40 (Some Extent-SE); 1.81-2.60 (Little Extent-LtE); 1.00-1.80 (Very Little Extent-VLtE)

Based on assessments of the managers, item no. 2, with a weighted mean score of 4.00 and interpreted as “large extent,” obtained the highest extent of implementation of the selection process in terms of onboarding, while item no. 3 received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean score of 3.45 and interpreted as “large extent.”

Table 14

The Summary of the Extent of Implementation of the Selection Process

Selection Process	Managers		Staff	
	WM	QI	WM	QI
1. Assessment Procedure	3.93	LgE	3.87	LgE
2. Deal Closing	3.09	SE	3.68	LgE
3. Onboarding	3.65	LgE	3.76	LgE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.56	LgE	3.77	LgE

Note. Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Very Large Extent-VLgE); 3.41-4.20 (Large Extent-LgE); 2.61-3.40 (Some Extent-SE); 1.81-2.60 (Little Extent-LtE); 1.00-1.80 (Very Little Extent-VLtE)

Based on assessments of the managers, item no. 1, with a weighted mean score of 3.93 and interpreted as “large extent,” obtained the highest extent of implementation of the selection process in terms of its variables, while item no. 2 received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean score of 3.09 and interpreted as “some extent.”

Table 15

The Significant Difference in the Assessments of the Respondents in the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment and Selection Process When Grouped According to Age

Age	Ave.	SD	F	p	Decision	Interpretation
Recruitment Process						
<u>Needs Anticipation</u>						
20-29 years old	3.73	0.17	1.82	0.165	Accept Ho	Not Significant
30-39 years old	3.76	0.14				
40-49 years old	3.49	0.19				
50-59 years old	3.64	0.26				
60 years old and older	4.00	0.58				
<u>Job Analysis</u>						
20-29 years old	3.94	0.22	5.95	0.002	Reject Ho	Significant
30-39 years old	3.97	0.19				
40-49 years old	4.08	0.15				
50-59 years old	3.95	0.22				
60 years old and older	4.44	0.27				
<u>Pool Development</u>						
20-29 years old	4.09	0.12	16.71	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
30-39 years old	4.03	0.17				
40-49 years old	4.00	0.17				

50-59 years old	3.79	0.19
60 years old and older	4.57	0.25

Age	Ave.	SD	F	p	Decision	Interpretation
Selection Process						
<u>Assessment Procedure</u>						
20-29 years old	3.99	0.17	8.73	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
30-39 years old	3.79	0.18				
40-49 years old	3.87	0.26				
50-59 years old	3.69	0.31				
60 years old and older	4.53	0.30				
<u>Deal Closing</u>						
20-29 years old	3.55	0.25	3.40	0.028	Reject Ho	Significant
30-39 years old	3.74	0.16				
40-49 years old	3.48	0.15				
50-59 years old	3.51	0.17				
60 years old and older	4.07	0.55				
<u>Onboarding</u>						
20-29 years old	3.68	0.20	3.54	0.024	Reject Ho	Significant
30-39 years old	3.91	0.21				
40-49 years old	3.68	0.22				
50-59 years old	3.44	0.28				
60 years old and older	3.93	0.28				

Note. The p-value is significant below alpha 0.05

Based on the gathered data, the computed *p*-values for the recruitment and selection process in terms of job analysis [*p* = 0.002], pool development [*p* = 0.000], assessment procedure [*p* = 0.000], deal closing [*p* = 0.028], and onboarding [*p* = 0.024] are below the level of alpha at 0.05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis and showing a significant difference, while the needs anticipation [*p* = 0.165] is above the alpha level of significance, indicating acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Table 16

The Significant Difference in the Assessments of the Respondents in the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment and Selection Process When Grouped According to Sex

Sex	Ave.	SD	t	p	Decision	Interpretation
Recruitment Process						
<u>Needs Anticipation</u>						
Male	3.63	0.19	-1.15	0.287	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Female	3.76	0.14				
<u>Job Analysis</u>						
Male	3.83	0.18	-3.21	0.009	Reject Ho	Significant
Female	4.17	0.19				
<u>Pool Development</u>						
Male	3.90	0.13	-3.61	0.004	Reject Ho	Significant
Female	4.17	0.16				

Sex	Ave.	SD	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	Decision	Interpretation
Selection Process						
<u>Assessment Procedure</u>						
Male	3.80	0.13	-1.49	0.181	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Female	3.96	0.19				
<u>Deal Closing</u>						
Male	3.57	0.06	-1.40	0.220	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Female	3.68	0.17				
<u>Onboarding</u>						
Male	3.64	0.17	-2.14	0.065	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Female	3.86	0.15				

Note. *The p-value is significant below alpha 0.05*

Based on the gathered data, the computed *p*-values for the recruitment and selection process in terms of job analysis [*p* = 0.009] and pool development [*p* = 0.004] are below the level of alpha at 0.05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis and showing a significant difference, while the needs anticipation [*p* = 0.287], assessment procedure [*p* = 0.181], deal closing [*p* = 0.220], and onboarding [*p* = 0.065] are above the alpha level of significance, indicating acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Table 17

The Significant Difference in the Assessments of the Respondents in the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment and Selection Process When Grouped According to Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Ave.	SD	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	Decision	Interpretation
Recruitment Process						
<u>Needs Anticipation</u>						
Bachelor's Degree	3.80	0.16	7.25	0.009	Reject Ho	Significant
Master's Degree	3.38	0.20				
Doctoral Degree	3.69	0.18				
<u>Job Analysis</u>						
Bachelor's Degree	4.12	0.19	15.32	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Master's Degree	3.86	0.11				
Doctoral Degree	3.52	0.25				
<u>Pool Development</u>						
Bachelor's Degree	4.10	0.15	11.99	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Master's Degree	3.80	0.15				
Doctoral Degree	4.13	0.12				
Selection Process						
<u>Assessment Procedure</u>						
Bachelor's Degree	3.99	0.22	6.27	0.014	Reject Ho	Significant
Master's Degree	3.58	0.16				
Doctoral Degree	3.80	0.16				
<u>Deal Closing</u>						
Bachelor's Degree	3.83	0.18	56.26	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Master's Degree	3.40	0.13				

Doctoral Degree	2.82	0.14				
Onboarding						
Bachelor's Degree	3.82	0.15	3.06	0.084	Accept	Not Significant
Master's Degree	3.63	0.21			Ho	
Doctoral Degree	3.55	0.18				

Note. The *p*-value is significant below alpha 0.05

Based on the gathered data, the computed *p*-values for the recruitment and selection process in terms of needs anticipation [*p* = 0.009], job analysis [*p* = 0.000], pool development [*p* = 0.000], assessment procedure [*p* = 0.014], and deal closing [*p* = 0.000] are below the level of alpha at 0.05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis and showing a significant difference, while the onboarding [*p* = 0.084] is above the alpha level of significance, indicating acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Table 18

The Significant Difference in the Assessments of the Respondents in the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment and Selection Process When Grouped According to Designation

Designation	Ave.	SD	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	Decision	Interpretation
Recruitment Process						
Needs Anticipation						
Manager	3.44	0.27	-2.03	0.082	Accept	Not Significant
Staff	3.72	0.17			Ho	
Job Analysis						
Manager	3.26	0.19	-7.83	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Staff	4.08	0.18				
Pool Development						
Manager	3.87	0.19	-2.10	0.060	Accept	Not Significant
Staff	4.05	0.13			Ho	
Selection Process						
Assessment Procedure						
Manager	3.93	0.12	0.65	0.534	Accept	Not Significant
Staff	3.87	0.16			Ho	
Deal Closing						
Manager	3.09	0.20	-5.36	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Staff	3.68	0.14				
Onboarding						
Manager	3.65	0.22	-0.88	0.408	Accept	Not Significant
Staff	3.76	0.15			Ho	

Note. The *p*-value is significant below alpha 0.05

Based on the gathered data, the computed *p*-values for the recruitment and selection process in terms of job analysis [*p* = 0.000] and deal closing [*p* = 0.001] are below the level of alpha at 0.05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis and showing a significant difference, while the needs anticipation [*p* = 0.082], pool development [*p* = 0.060], assessment procedure [*p* = 0.534], and onboarding [*p* = 0.408] are above the alpha level of significance, indicating acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Table 19

The Significant Difference in the Assessments of the Respondents in the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment and Selection Process When Grouped According to Years of Employment at the Company

Years of Employment at the Company	Ave.	SD	F	p	Decision	Interpretation
Recruitment Process						
<u>Needs Anticipation</u>						
1-5 years	3.80	0.22	0.95	0.455	Accept Ho	Not Significant
6-10 years	3.58	0.14				
11-15 years	3.78	0.11				
16-20 years	3.56	0.32				
21 years and above	3.48	0.59				
Years of Employment at the Company						
<u>Job Analysis</u>						
1-5 years	3.96	0.23	1.99	0.128	Accept Ho	Not Significant
6-10 years	4.01	0.18				
11-15 years	4.13	0.22				
16-20 years	3.85	0.28				
21 years and above	3.77	0.29				
<u>Pool Development</u>						
1-5 years	4.23	0.10	13.46	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
6-10 years	3.90	0.18				
11-15 years	3.94	0.13				
16-20 years	3.68	0.20				
21 years and above	4.43	0.35				
Selection Process						
<u>Assessment Procedure</u>						
1-5 years	3.98	0.25	3.33	0.030	Reject Ho	Significant
6-10 years	3.76	0.18				
11-15 years	3.93	0.21				
16-20 years	3.58	0.14				
21 years and above	4.12	0.41				
<u>Deal Closing</u>						
1-5 years	3.78	0.20	16.86	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
6-10 years	3.51	0.11				
11-15 years	3.52	0.17				
16-20 years	3.33	0.08				
21 years and above	4.12	0.23				
<u>Onboarding</u>						
1-5 years	3.77	0.18	1.89	0.152	Accept Ho	Not Significant
6-10 years	3.84	0.18				
11-15 years	3.73	0.17				
16-20 years	3.44	0.30				

21 years and above	3.68	0.33
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Note. The p-value is significant below alpha 0.05

Based on the gathered data, the computed p-values for the recruitment and selection process in terms of pool development [$p = 0.000$], assessment procedure [$p = 0.030$], and deal closing [$p = 0.00$] are below the level of alpha at 0.05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis and showing a significant difference, while the needs anticipation [$p = 0.455$], job analysis [$p = 0.128$], and onboarding [$p = 0.152$] are above the alpha level of significance, indicating acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Discussion

The majority of the respondents involved in the recruitment and selection process of the company were 30-39 years old, while the minority were 60 years old and older; the highest proportion of the respondents were in their 30s. Moreover, the majority of the respondents involved in the recruitment and selection process of the company were predominantly males, while a minor proportion were females.

In terms of the respondents' educational attainment, the majority of the respondents involved in the recruitment and selection process of the company were bachelor's degree holders, while the minority were doctoral degree holders and the highest proportion of the respondents were college graduates. The majority of the respondents involved in the recruitment and selection process of the company were predominantly staff members, while a minor proportion were designated with management responsibilities.

The majority of the respondents involved in the recruitment and selection process of the company have predominantly been employed for about 1-5 years, while a minor proportion have been employed for 21 years and above. The highest proportion of the respondents were in the early stages of their employment at the company.

The findings in the recruitment process' implementation were to an acceptable standard, that the company made sure to consistently carry out a proactive study of future requirements and continuously evaluate the status of some of the best personnel that is certain to depart. Furthermore, the results demonstrated that, to plan strategically for the year that lies ahead, the company also examines the proposed job description and structure of operations to make sure that it fully satisfies the needs of the company and that hiring needs and goals are aligned.

Nevertheless, both managers and staff pointed out that there are still gaps in the facts provided above, indicating that the company should concentrate more on establishing a recruitment plan to help expedite the hiring process and identify positions that would require encompassing soon. This is an opportunity to combine company goals and skill gaps with hiring actions in order to proactively plan for the upcoming year. It goes considerably beyond simply knowing what roles need to be filled soon. This suggested that in order to

meet the demands of modern business objectives, the company should utilize the results to improve the way its recruitment practices are implemented in terms of needs anticipation.

The findings demonstrated also how the company decided how to evaluate employee performance and made sure the position and the prospective employee were a good fit. Furthermore, the managers' observations indicated that the company additionally performs an adequate task of outlining the responsibilities of the role and has a thorough grasp of the business aims related to it.

The company should, however, continue putting an emphasis on the lists of qualities and skills required by potential applicants and even find innovative methods to fine-tune the function for improved efficacy in spite of the aforementioned facts. Essentially, the extent of implementation of the recruitment process in terms of pool development obtained overall weighted means of 3.87 and 4.05 as assessed by the managers and staff, respectively, and both were interpreted as "large extent.". The findings demonstrated that the company made sure to align its expansion strategies with employee advancement and succession planning. Additionally, the results of the investigation demonstrated that the company additionally placed importance on reviewing the succession plan each time a job becomes open or a need to fill one arises.

Even so, both respondents (managers and staff) pointed out that there are still gaps in the information provided, which means the company should emphasize more on expanding the pool of candidates for a position in order to attract qualified applicants. It should focus on the use cost-effective e-recruiting systems, which enable an organization to gather, store, and process information quickly and use it for external sourcing in this new normal of the recruitment process. This agrees to the conclusion made MBA Knowledge Base in 2021 that company can use e-recruiting to swiftly gather data, store and retrieve information, and then utilize this information for external sourcing as needed (MBA Knowledge Base, 2021). Recruiters for human resources can broaden their prospect pool by doing this. They may access a wider pool of possible candidates when they publish about a job opening, which also broadens their selection process. They are therefore able to choose the right applicants (Khanna, 2021). This emphasized that in order to cope with the demands of present-day business targets, the company should apply the pool development findings to strengthen the way its processes for recruiting employees are implemented.

Overall, the extent of implementation of the recruitment process in terms of its variables obtained overall weighted means of 3.52 and 3.95 as assessed by the managers and staff, respectively, and both were interpreted as "large extent."

The study's findings revealed a satisfactory level of implementation of the recruitment process. According to both respondents, the results showed that the company made sure that a candidate pool for a job offer or opportunity was routinely developed by using both internal and external methods of discovering prospects.

Closing is a crucial step in the hiring process. The company should make it a point to find out what matters most to the best applicants (McConnachie, 2019). One of the most rewarding and difficult parts of recruitment is closing top applicants in a highly competitive environment. Convincing the top personnel to join the company is a blend of abilities, tactics, and mentality. It is important to fully understand their expectations, preferences, and motivations. This meant that to meet the company's present demand, it would be necessary to use the results to enhance the way its selection process operates.

Moreover, for comparisons, as can be gleaned from the average means, it showed that those respondents belonged to 60 years old and older [60 years old and older>other age groups] perceived a higher extent of implementation across variables of recruitment and selection process compared to other age groups.

Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the assessments of the respondents in the extent of implementation of the recruitment and selection process in terms of job analysis, pool development, assessment procedure, deal closing, and onboarding when they were grouped according to age.

Moreover, as can be gleaned from the average means, it showed that those female respondents perceived a higher extent of implementation in terms of job analysis and pool development compared to the male group of respondents.

Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the assessments of the respondents in the extent of implementation of the recruitment and selection process in terms of job analysis and pool development when they were grouped according to sex.

Moreover, for comparisons, as can be gleaned from the average means, it showed that those respondents with bachelor's degrees in terms of needs anticipation, job analysis, assessment procedure, and deal closing [Bachelor's degree>other groups] as well as those respondents with doctoral degrees in terms of pool development [Doctoral degree>other groups] perceived a higher extent of implementation compared to other educational attainment groups.

Furthermore, as can be gleaned from the average means, it showed that those staff respondents perceived a higher extent of implementation in terms of job analysis and deal closing compared to assessments made by the managers. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the assessments of the respondents in the extent of implementation of the recruitment and selection process in terms of job analysis and deal closing when they were grouped according to designation.

Likewise, for comparisons, as can be gleaned from the average means, it showed that those respondents who have been employed for 21 years and above perceived a higher extent of implementation in terms of pool development, assessment procedure, and deal closing [21 years and above>other groups] compared to other years of employment at the company groups.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the above findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn by the researcher:

The study showed that the highest proportion of the respondents involved in the recruitment and selection process were in their 30s, females, holders of bachelor's degrees, staff members, and were in the early stages of their employment at the company.

The study found that the company effectively implemented its recruitment process, creating a candidate pool for job offers using both internal and external methods. However, gaps were identified, suggesting the anticipation of the need for more staff observations and managers' perceptions of job analysis. To better understand the job's complexity, context, responsibilities, and practices, the company should conduct proactive analysis of future demands, continuously evaluate potential candidate pools, and generate periodic forecasts of needs. This will help the business adapt to the current environment and improve its recruitment process.

The investigation revealed that the company's selection process was effectively implemented, with a successful assessment procedure indicating a candidate's fit for the role and company culture. The onboarding process was methodical and orderly, aiming to encourage commitment and job satisfaction. However, there are still gaps in the data gathered, and the company should focus more on deal closing, particularly signing employment agreements with highly qualified candidates. Respondents noted that the results could be used to enhance the selection process to meet the company's current demand. This would require addressing the data gaps and improving the selection process.

The study found that, when respondents were categorized based on their profiles, there was a substantial difference in the assessments provided by the two groups of respondents (managers and staff) regarding the extent of the recruiting and selection process's implementation. This suggested that, in order to conduct a specific intervention based on differences in observation applicable to each category of variables, a significant difference in the respondents' observations regarding the extent of the implementation of the recruitment and selection process should be employed.

The following recommendations were proposed based on the findings and conclusions of the study:

1. It is recommended that future research address the shortcomings of the current study, potentially including the inclusion of more companies in various Chinese regions for comparative analysis and broader study conclusions. Also, it must be noted that that strategy development and post-hire evaluation be developed to fill up the gaps found and improve the company's recruitment and selection process over time.
2. Future research should employ qualitative approaches through interviews and focus group discussions to elucidate distinctions based on respondents' observations to confirm the various points of view conveyed by the respondents.
3. The study recommended utilizing the proposed program development to improve the effectiveness of the recruitment and selection process for the company.

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